

Impact of Job Stress on Job Performance with Moderating Role of Workplace Spirituality of Police Force Employees.

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Abstract

The purpose of the study portrays the impact of various job stress factors (i.e work overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility) on employees' job performance with moderating role of workplace spirituality. Data was collected through purposive and convenience sampling techniques of non-probability. Police's force of KPK, Province, Pakistan was used as a population for the current study. Questionnaire was distributed to the sample of N 385 out of total population of N 63,225 police employees. Out of 385 respondents, 295 employees responded. Data was analyzed through SPSS Version no.21 and AMOS 24. Reliability test was done through Cronbach's alpha values regarding the various instruments of study. Moreover, SEM was used for the measurement and structural model. Structural model method was adopted to confirm the proposed hypotheses of research study. To explore the moderating role of workplace spirituality between various job stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility) and job performance, multi-groups analysis method was used. Results reveal that there is significance and negative association between job stressors of the study and job performance. Moderating relationship of workplace spirituality was observed between role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development, role responsibility and job performance. Research was limited to police's employees of KPK, Pakistan. The research study is expected to contribute in the growing empirical research on job stressors and the underexplored area of workplace spirituality amongst police official operating in stressful environment. The study suggests development and practice of a systematic program that helps to argument prevalent degree of workplace spirituality and overcome job stressors and increase job performance.

Key words: Job Stressor (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development, role responsibility), workplace spirituality, job performance, Police personnel

1. Introduction

In this era of globalization many businesses face different challenges. Challenges can affect the individuals' or employees' lives. Individuals if have abilities and skills then they can turn the challenges into opportunities effectively and efficiently (Ristovska & Ristovska, 2014). For the retention purpose, employees of the organizations strive to provide both good qualitative and quantitative results. To obtain such results there is hard work required by the employees. According to Awan et al. (2021), for the achievement of good results at working place many times employees confront difficult and unavoidable situations. Employees cannot avoid from

these situations and resultantly engird them badly in stress. Stress at the job may give negative consequences. Stress varies employee to employee.

Stress at workplace arises due to various sources such as working environment, commuting stress, and discrimination in salaries, bonuses and different management styles (Amponsah-Tawiah & Annor, 2016; Artz, 2008; Mc Vicar, 2016). Similarly, few of the job stressors that can be work over load, role conflict, role ambiguity, lengthy career development plan and responsibilities of other people or role responsibility affect the employees' well-being (Khamisa & Peltzer, 2016; Bokti & Talib, 2009; Qureshi & Ramay, 2006). According to Nevi & Peranginangin (2019) well-being of employees reduces their motivational level worsened. Napitupulu et al. (2017) suggest that low level of motivation many times lead to the poor performance of working personnel. Ultimately, poor performance of each employee of the organization reflects the poor organizational performance (Tedla, 2016). Therefore, it is to be said that an organizational performance is the combination or collection of individuals' performance (Kim & Kim, 2020).

In past, many techniques were used to minimize the job stress. To overcome the stress at the job, Islamic work Ethics (I.W.E) and its different dimensions were adopted. Exercise was used to minimize the stress. To cope the stress workplace spirituality has used in very few studies because spirituality improve the health level that ultimately emerge the person to perform well at the job place. Meitasari et al. (2018) recommend that spirituality stimulates the hidden potential. It is a source of nourishing the skills and working capabilities of a person.

Workplace spirituality used as moderator between dark trait and instigated incivility by (Lata & Chaudhry, 2020). Kumar & Kumar (2014) also used the construct of workplace spirituality between work load and health of employees. Moderation effect of workplace spirituality was explored between role overload and job satisfaction (Altaf & Awan, 2011). The study conducted by Lyer & Deshmukh (2018) workplace spirituality was examined as a moderator between role overload, role conflict and role ambiguity of job stressor (role ambiguity) and job outcome i.e job satisfaction. This study emphasizes to fill gap of the moderating effect of workplace spirituality between various job stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility) and job performance on working employees of KP Police simultaneously.

Organizational performance is direct outcome of corresponding performance of its employees at work place. Healthy and enthusiastic workforce performs well and employees confronting stress at the job on consistent range evolve their performance to serious extent. Organizations of all types of natures and sizes to strive in provision of stress free environment to the working personnel for positive consequences. Problem in hand for this research study to find out the association between various job stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility) and job performance of employees. Research study also explores effect of moderation of workplace spirituality on the relationship between job stressors and job performance amid police personnel at different job places in the geographical areas of KPK. This study has objectives and aim to analyze the relationship between job stressors and job performance, to investigate the moderation effect of workplace spirituality on the relationship between job stressors and job performance and to evaluate the relationship critically among the constructs of the study job stressors, workplace spirituality and job performance of KP police work force.

There can be observed few of implications which can be extracted from the study for the multiple organizations in Pakistani culture. Stress at the job with its different factors reduces the level of well-being and motivational level of employees and mean while the spirituality level boost up the not the motivational level but also increases the level of individuals performance level. Workplace spirituality dimensions if implemented in the organizations then their performance at micro and macro level can be enhanced. Dimensions of workplace spirituality such as honesty, recitation of holy books in relax time, adoption of silence before starting of tasks and friendly relationship with working colleagues can be fruitful for the managers and owners if the dimensions are implemented properly. Workplace spirituality along with its facets can be adopted by the trainers for the capacity building programs widely.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Transactional and coping theory

Theory of transactional presented by Lazarus & Folkman (1984) highlights the two characters as primary appraisal and secondary appraisal. Primary appraisal was linked with stress and its sources and the secondary appraisal stated the ways / methods to cope the stress and its intensity. Role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility are the stress sources creation which affect the employee's job performance badly and interference of workplace spirituality as secondary appraisal construct enhances the level of police force employee's performance.

2.2 Job Performance

Job performance can be measured in the forms of profit of each person earned for the organization either produced number of units by individuals in specific and limited time frame (Qamar & Baloch, 2011). According to Ali et al. (2011) job performance is measured number of achieved tasks or multiple tasks. It covers two dimensions in role task performance and extra role task performance. Ke & Deng (2018) define and explain the term of job performance is as "job performance is a combination of intra role and extra role performance". In- role performance is a performance wherein employees perform their duties according to the formal rules and procedures and extra role performance reflect that when employees of the organizations accomplish their tasks or objectives beyond the following of specified rules and procedures.

2.3 Job Stress

Alias et al. (2018) remark that stress at the job arises due to various external and internal factors of working environment. These factors can be work to family conflict, family to work conflict, Breaking news, economic and financial losses, loss of life of bereavement, pay and bonuses discrimination, workload, attitude of bosses, attitude of peers, role ambiguity, working environment and changing the structure of the organization. Other job stressors can be role conflict, responsibilities of other employees and fear of termination from the job.

2.4 Workload and Job Performance

Rizwan et al. (2014) recommend that work overload is a source of job stress which happens due to completing the task or working activity of spending more times even beyond the official working hours or in public holidays. Employee of the organization does more work than his

intellectual capacity and given resources. On the other side, qualitative over work is occurred when employee of the working entity faces the work complication from his skills and capabilities to accomplish (Nevi & Peranginangin, 2019). According to Mital & Bhakar (2017) intensity of job stress which is happened due to workload impacted the job performance badly. In other words, the more level of workload may reduce the level of job performance and low level of workload can be the reason of high performance. Authors also observe the significant relationship between workload and job performance. In continuation of the results exploration Ali and Farooqi (2014) found the significant association between the jobs overload and job performance of banking sector employees.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between role overload and job performance

2.5 Role Conflict and Job Performance

Warraich et al. (2014) define that role conflict is a phenomenon wherein contradicted roles are assigned to the employees. Jobs and duties that are contrary to the job incumbents of their job responsibilities and nature of duties can create stress at the working place. Such type of job stress depicts the lethargic well-being of employees. Finally, this leads to low level of attitude towards the low level of performance (Mai and Hai, 2016). In this context, Jacomossol, Schlup & Zonatto (2018) conducted research and examined the negative and significant relation between role conflict and job performance. Significant association was also analyzed between role conflict and employees' job performance in empirical study on call centers working personnel in Surabaya (Lukiastuti, 2021).

H₂: There is a significant relationship between role conflict and job performance.

2.6 Role Ambiguity and Job Performance

The term role ambiguity means ambiguous roles towards the tasks achievement, unclear directions and uncertainty of roles of a working entity about the objectives or working activities to complete (Sunada, 2018). Amilin (2017) suggests that ambiguous and uncertain directions to any task may confuse the person and cause a creation of stress. Moreover, author finds the relationship one of the job stressors i.e. role ambiguity and job performance. Yang et al. (2015) remarked that here is an inverse relationship between role ambiguity and job performance. Role ambiguity is source of hindrance stressor which decreases not only the job performance but can also affect the working environment badly. Authors investigated the significant relationship between role ambiguity and employees job performance.

H₃: There is a significant relationship between role ambiguity and job performance

2.7 Career Development and Job Performance

Development of career with reference to employees has lot of importance because development is also beneficial for the employees which link with the development of organizations. In era of technological advancement, there is much need of employee's development (Napitupulu et al., 2017). Even today, in the modern era, many organizations have lengthy and complex procedure for the development of employees. Promotion and their (employees) turn to training for the capacity building programs often take many years / time. Such lengthy and complex procedure can instigate to employees to quit from the organization (Imran et al., 2014). According to Dialok & Nkechi (2017) employees flour mills did not meet the seasonal targets

of output and resultantly organizational performance gone down. The results also provide significance association between career development and job performance.

H₄: There is a significant relationship between career development and job performance

2.8 Role Responsibility and Job Performance

Responsibilities, beyond the workers' job description may be the reason of job stress. Responsibilities of other employees at the job place can create hindrance to achieve personal objectives or daily working activities (Khan and Mashikh, 2017). Past studies conducted by Amoako-Asiedu and Obuobisa-Darko (2017) recommended that negative consequences from job stress were received in the form of health disorder and rude behavior. Passive and sluggish behaviour of the employees provided poor performance. Al-KhasaWneh (2015) suggest that the both constructs role responsibility and job performance has strong and significant relationship with each other.

H₅: There is a significant relationship between role responsibility and job performance

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

2.9 Workplace Spirituality as a moderator between job stressors and job performance

Employees those who are found honest and have friendly relationship with working employees are more productive. Spirituality at workplace has moderation effect between role overload as job stressor and job satisfaction which is considered one of the job outcomes because workplace spirituality minimizes the level of stress intensity and brings positive consequences (Altaf&Awan, 2011). Ahmed &Omer (2011) explored the moderation effect of workplace spirituality between role ambiguity (job stressor) and job satisfaction. Similarly, moderation effect of workplace spirituality was observed on the relationship between various job stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity)and job satisfaction of audit workers (Meitasari et al., 2018).Therefore, this study focuses on to investigate the moderating role of workplace spirituality between this study's job stressors like as role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility and job performance collectively on police force of KPK.

H₆: There is a moderation effect of workplace spirituality between job stressors and job performance

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants / Subjects

Population of the study was kept to police force employees from BPS-09 Havaladar to BPS 19 Senior Superintendent of Police S.S.P / A.I.G of KPK which is the North West province of Pakistan. Police force of KPK is approximately 63,225. From said population of the study, proportionate sampling method was used to collect the data. Finally, 385 employees were determined to collect the data from various police stations, deputed at other working places and departments.

3.2 Procedure

Data was distributed and collected through convenient sampling technique of non-probability sampling. Cross sectional technique was used to get the response. Data was collected from 295 employees, out of total sampling respondents which is appropriate sample size to analyze the data (Hair et al., 2014). In other words approximately 77% respondents provided the response.

3.3 Instrument / Measures:

Instruments were divided into four parts like as demographic characteristics, job stressors variables, workplace spirituality and job performance. Demographic constructs were prepared and developed by the researcher. Rests of the instruments were adopted in the study. Questionnaire on job stress factors consisting on role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility was adopted of developed instrument Ivancevich & Matteson (1980). Instrument of workplace spirituality was also adopted in the study and which was developed and used(Sheng & Chen, 2012).This measurement scale covers the diemnsion of Workplace Spirituality such as trust, honesty, relationship with other employess and integrity.Scale of job performance was used in that study of prepaed by (williams &Anderson, 1991). Five likert scale of close ended mthod which ranges from strongly disagree to strongly agree was priortized over the other methods.

3.4 Data Analysis

Pilot testing was done before the collection of actual data. According to Trece and Trece (1977) there should be 10 % of the the total sample size to data distribution for the pilot testing. Therefore, data was distributed to 38 employees and out of them 33 employees responded. SPSS 21 version was used for the data analysis. In this phase, reliability analysis of various instruments of the study was detected. From the job stressors instrument 9 items were deleted out of five dimensions and reliability was improved to 0.75, 0.78, 0.71, 0.68 and 0.79 of role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility. . Similarly, same method was used with other two constructs that were workplace spirituality and job performance. Reliability of both constructs were reached to 0.77 and 0.66, respectively. Out of 27 items of workplace spirituality measurement scale 12 items were removed and out of 21 items of job performance scale 11 items were also discarded.

4. Results

Data of the study was gathered from 295 respondents. Information regarding each segment of demographics is given below. Items of the study scales were tested through two methods. These methods were item to total correlation and reliability analysis. Item no.10 of workoverload was eliminated. Similarly, Item no. 5 was removed from the instrument of workplace spirituality. Finally, item no 12 was also removed from the job performance measurement scale. Value of three items from respective scales did not fulfill the criteria of item to total correlation.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics

Demographic		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	270	92.0	92.0	92.0
	Female	15	8.0	8.0	100
	Total	295	100.0	100.0	
Marital Status	Single	56	19.0	19.0	19.0
	Married	239	81.0	81.0	100.0
	Total	295	100.0	100.0	
Age	18-30 years	86	29.0	29.0	29.0
	31-40 years	117	40.0	40.0	69.0
	41-50 years	54	18.0	18.0	87.0
	51-60 years	38	13.0	13.0	100.0
	Total	295	100.0	100.0	
Level of Education	Matriculation or equal	86	29.0	29.0	29.0
	Intermediate or equal	55	19.0	19.0	48.0
	Graduation or equal	71	24.0	24.0	72.0
	Post graduate	40	13.0	13.0	85.0
	MPhil or equal	43	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	295	100.0	100.0	
Designation	Havaldars	140	47.0	47.0	47.0
	Asstt. Sub inspectors	57	19.0	19.0	66.0
	Sub inspectors	26	9.0	9.0	75.0
	Inspectors	38	13.0	13.0	88.0
	DSPs or ASPs	25	8.0	8.0	96.0
	SSP or AIG	9	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	295	100.0	100.0	
	Work Experience	1-20 years	195	66.0	66.0
21 and above years		100	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total		295	100.0	100.0	

These values were .269 from instrument of work overload, .256 workplace spirituality and .269 of job performance. According to Hair et al. (2014) minimum value of item of measurement scale should be .3. Due to this process reliability of each instrument was improved. Table 2 is about the scales purification which was done through EFA technique. Reliability analysis of each instrument can be observed from the following table.

Table. 2 Reliability analysis of research scales

Constructs/Items	Code	1 st analysis Item-to-total correlation	Cronbach Alpha	2 nd analysis Item-to-total correlation	Cronbach Alpha
Job Stressors					
Role Overload	RO		.839		.894
	RO2	.647		.674	
	RO3	.706		.712	
	RO4	.663		.676	
	RO6	.659		.667	
	RO7	.634		.657	
	RO8	.683		.744	
	RO9	.668		.716	
	RO10	.269		Excluded*	
Role Conflict	RC		.851		.851
	RC3	.667		.667	
	RC4	.731		.731	
	RC5	.772		.772	
Role Ambiguity	RA		.804		.804
	RA2	.595		.595	
	RA3	.680		.680	
	RA4	.681		.681	
Carer Development	CD		.862		.862
	CD1	.713		.713	
	CD3	.678		.678	
	CD4	.723		.723	
	CD5	.725		.725	
Role Responsibility	RR		.800		.800
	RR3	.630		.630	
	RR4	.671		.671	
	RR5	.632		.632	
Workplace Spirituality			.934		.945
	WS1	.785		.789	
	WS2	.745		.749	
	WS3	.686		.689	
	WS4	.719		.709	
	WS5	.256		Excluded*	
	WS8	.694		.715	
	WS15	.677		.681	
	WS16	.716		.721	
	WS17	.677		.687	
	WS18	.685		.688	
	WS19	.693		.701	
	WS20	.763		.776	
	WS21	.761		.760	
	WS21	.656		.654	
	WS26	.714		.702	
Job Performance			.914		.933
	JP1	.778		.692	
	JP2	.735		.648	
	JP3	.746		.609	
	JP4	.740		.610	
	JP6	.776		.641	
	JP8	.708		.584	
	JP9	.775		.681	
	JP10	.673		.653	
	JP11	.757		.692	
	JP12	.269		Excluded*	

4.2 The Measurement Model

To find out the fitness of data CFA test was adopted. Hair et al., (2014) suggested significant at P value less than 0.001 ($X^2=1476.374$, $p<0.001$; $X^2/df=1.470$). As for dealing with other values of goodness of fit both the normed fit index (NFI) and the comparative fit index (CFI) scored were observed 0.873 and 0.955 respectively. Values of NFI and CFI crossed the acceptable value i.e. 0.9(Hair et al., 2014). Moreover, (RMSEA=0.038) root mean square error of approximation was analyzed. According to the Hair et al., (2014) value of RMSEA can be in the range of 0.3 and 0.8. Therefore, all the values of model fit as discussed are found accordingly.

Table. 3 Results of Measurement Model

Construct	Item	Loading	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)			
Role Overload	RO2	.779	0.921	0.623			
	RO3	.806					
	RO4	.779					
	RO6	.783					
	RO7	.780					
	RO8	.815					
	RO9	.784					
	Role Conflict	RC3			.779	0.862	0.676
		RC4			.828		
RC5		.858					
Role Ambiguity	RA2	.697	0.805	0.581			
	RA3	.859					
	RA4	.720					
Career Development	CD1	.800	0.886	0.660			
	CD3	.811					
	CD4	.827					
	CD5	.812					
	RR3	.767					
Role Responsibility	RR4	.810	0.831	0.621			
	RR5	.786					
Job Performance	JP2	.795	0.933	0.610			
	JP3	.770					
	JP4	.769					
	JP6	.809					
	JP8	.748					
	JP9	.813					
	JP10	.720					
	JP11	.775					
	JP1	.820					
	Work Place Spirituality	WS1			.815	0.938	0.538
		WS3			.676		
WS4		.720					
WS8		.731					
WS15		.683					
WS16		.757					
WS17		.725					
WS18		.719					
WS19		.730					
WS20		.779					
WS26		.737					
WS22	.687						
WS21	.766						

Model fit indices: $X^2=1476.374$, $p < 0.001$; $X^2/df = 1.470$; $NFI = 0.873$, $CFI = 0.955$; $NFI = 0.873$; $RMSEA = 0.038$
Note: (CR) = $(\sum \text{Factor loadings})^2 / [(\sum \text{Factor loadings})^2 + (\sum \text{Error variances})^2]$;
(AVE) = $(\sum \text{Factor loadings})^2 / [(\sum \text{factor loadings})^2 + (\sum \text{error variances})]$.

Two steps approach and guidelines set by Anderson and Gerbing 1988 were followed by the researcher. In first step of the two steps approach convergent validity and reliability are necessary. For achieving the convergent validity model must to satisfy three conditions such as the loadings of factor should be greater than 0.5 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988), value of composite

reliability should be also greater than value of 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 2004) and value of average variance extracted (AVE) should be >0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Table 3 reflects that the model which fulfills the criteria. Furthermore, discriminant validity, following Hair et al. (2018) suggestions, square root of AVE was compared to inter-construct correlation. The value of square root of AVE must be greater than the inter-construct correlation between the construct. As can be seen in Table 4, the square root as shown on the diagonals of the table is greater than the inter-construct correlation values. This further suggests that discriminant validity is evident.

Table.4 Discriminant Validity of the Constructs

	Role Overload	Career Development	Role Conflict	Role Responsibility	Role Ambiguity	Work Place Spirituality	Job Performance
Role Overload	0.790						
Career Development	0.732***	0.813					
Role Conflict	0.714***	0.823***	0.822				
Role Responsibility	0.714***	0.686***	0.627***	0.788			
Role Ambiguity	0.576***	0.692***	0.743***	0.533***	0.762		
Workplace Spirituality	0.101†	0.083	0.070	0.111†	0.006	0.734	
Job Performance	-0.772***	-0.829***	-0.816***	-0.765***	-0.713***	-0.074	0.781

Note: Diagonal values represent square root of AVE while the other entries represent the square of correlation values.

Table.5 Results of Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta value	Standard error	Critical Ratio	P-value	Accepted/ Rejected
H1	Job_Per → R_O	-.144	.065	-2.557	.011	Accepted
H2	Job_Per → R_C	-.187	.097	-2.359	.018	Accepted
H3	Job_Per → R_A	-.139	.082	-2.483	.013	Accepted
H4	Job_Per → C_D	-.197	.092	-2.615	.009	Accepted
H5	Job_Per → R_R	-.173	.073	-2.752	.006	Accepted

Results of hypotheses testing can be examined from given below table no.5. Results regarding the first hypothesis depict that there is negative and significant relationship between work overload and Job performance which can be observed from i.e. standardized coefficient $\beta = -.144$ with i.e. p value .011. Results of hypothesis H2 indicate the relationship between role conflict and job performance. Statistical results with reference to second hypothesis such as $\beta = -.187$ and p value .018 suggest the association between role conflict and job performance which found negative and significance. Statistical results such as β value which is $-.139$ and p value .013 represent significance and negative interlink between role ambiguity and job performance. Significance and negative relationship were observed with rest of the two job stressors (career development and role responsibility) and job performance. Beta values and P

values of the H4 and H5 are found according to the proposed hypotheses and which is for H4 β value = $-.197$ and p value = $.009$ and for H5 β value = $-.173$ and p value = $.006$. So, findings recommend that H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄ and H₅ are proved and accepted.

4.3 Moderation Analysis

Results regarding the moderation effect of workplace spirituality between five job stressors and job performance can be examined through table 7 of structural modeling technique. Table shows that workplace spirituality plays a moderating role between multiple job stressors of the study which are Role overload, Role conflict, Role ambiguity, Career development and Role responsibility and Job performance. To explore the moderation effect multi group technique was used and which was also determined through high workplace spirituality group and low workplace spirituality group. Results support the hypothesis H6 through the path estimation values which are significant but having high level of workplace spirituality employees are performed well as compare to low level group of spirituality. Value of path estimation of high workplace spirituality employees is greater than of low level of workplace spirituality employees. Table 6 is about moderation effect of workplace spirituality with observed values of path estimation and critical or t ratio. Therefore, results support the hypothesis H6.

Table.6 Results of Moderation hypotheses regarding workplace spirituality

Path	High Level WPS		Low Level WPS		Critical ratio	Results
	R ²	Path Est.	R ²	Path Est.		
Job_Per → Job_St	68.6%	-.257**	61.2%	-.347***	-4.124	Supported

5. Discussion

Aim of this study to investigate the indicator which affect the job performance of policeforce's employees. Theses factors are denotaed job stressors. job stressors namely job overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility are the factors that influence the performance negatively. Theses are considered hindrance stressors.

According to table 5 of this study, a significant negative relationship between role overload and job performance is observed because P (sig.) value is $.011$ and Beta value is $-.144$. Results of this hypothesis i.e. H₁ are in line with the studies of concluding remarks (Mital & Bhakar, 2017). Numeric values with reference to H₁ explain burden of work is a cause of reduction in KPK's police employees output. On the other side, lower level of workload enhances their performance.

Role conflict, the second job stressor of the study reflects an inverse significant relationship with employees' job performance. Significance or p value is $.018$ and negative relationship is observed through Beta value which is also $-.187$. Findings of the study are accordance with the study's findings (Mai & Hai, 2016; Sutanto & Wiyono, 2017). This standardized coefficient value shows the negative relationship between role conflict and job performance. In other words, it is to be said that there is explored inverse relationship of the said variables (role conflict and job performance). Such relationship explains that multiple but opposed roles that are not according to the prescribed duties and job responsibilities of Police Act 1861 creates hindrances towards the achievement of tasks.

Role ambiguity is considered hindrance job stressors that shows opposed but significance relationship with the job performance because P (sig) value is found $.013$ which is not greater than 0.05 . Negative link is also examined between the role ambiguity and job performance from

the statistical results of Beta value which is $-.139$. The results are consistent with the concluding remarks (Kang et al., 2014).

Career Development is a stressor for job holders because stress is emerged when ill or lengthy policies of the department do not promote the employees within time specific time frame due to accomplishment of late DPCs or Selection Board committee. There is investigated significance along with negative relationship between career development and job performance. P value $.009$ and Beta value $-.197$ portray the significance and negative relationship between the constructs. This means that majority of the employees were performing their tasks poorly due to lengthy and complex governmental i.e. police department procedure. Conclusion regarding to the H4 is in line with the results of study conducted by (Dialok & Nkechi, 2017).

Finally, the H5 represents that there is detected negative and significance association between job stressor (role responsibility) and employees' job performance. Values of significance and negative can be observed from table 5 which are $.006$ and $-.173$ respectively. So, results of study conducted by (Amoako- Asiedu & Obuobisa-Darko, 2017) support the H5 of the study. In other words it is to be said in existence of role overload taking of work on discretion is a reason to decline the performance level of police employees.

Moderation effect of workplace spirituality was extracted through multi-groups technique. On the bases of critical ratios or t values and paths estimation two groups were formulated that were high workplace spirituality and low workplace spirituality. Table 6 shows that workplace spirituality plays moderating role upon the role overload and job performance. Statistical results regarding the six hypothesis H6 of the study describe that workplace spirituality has moderating role between all the job stressors of study and job performance which are according to the results (Altaf & Awan, 2011; Kumar & Kumar, 2014; Ahmed & Omer, 2011). Similarly, workplace spirituality plays moderating role between the other job stressors such as role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility and job performance. (Meitasari et al., 2018).

5.2 Theoretical Implications

This study emphasizes and concludes that the workload, role conflict and role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility have significance and negative influence on the employee's job performance. Findings as stated in previous chapter have not significantly contributed in the existing knowledge of supported theory development but also provide a new way to cope the stress or stressors at the job. Findings of the study also align with previous studies indicating that the workplace spirituality affects the job satisfaction and employees' productivity positively. The findings add to the body of literature on workplace spirituality, job satisfaction and employees' productivity. This research study proposes and validates the theory of interaction or transaction developed.

5.3 Managerial Implications

It implies that workplace spirituality which contributes in meaningfulness at work and self-realization helps in reducing the job stress and enhances job performance in return of leading to organizational productivity. Furthermore, high workplace spirituality creates high organizational commitment and quality of working life at the workplace. Hence, by the proper enactment of spirituality at work place from higher authority, the advancement of organization will come to start. More emphasize on utilization of workplace spirituality's practices, an organization can cope or minimize every issue relating to job stress or else efficiently and

effectively. Spirituality's practices are also fruitful beyond the working place. Practices of spirituality may be the reasons to get red from social issues. Therefore, it is also to be said that the more tilting towards spirituality makes the life level more satisfactory.

5.4 Research Limitations and Future Research

This study has few limitations such as police personnel KPK Pakistani culture were taken for the study population. Effect of hindrance stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility) was explored with moderation effect of workplace spirituality only on one job outcome i.e job performance. Convenient sampling technique was used to receive the respondent's response.

Other segments or sectors can be used as respondents or population in other cultures. For more generalized results, effect of same hindrance job stressor or others can be examined on the other job outcomes like as job embeddedness, job Satisfaction, turnover intentions and job burnout with the 'exercise' and 'work place ethics' as a moderators. In future, other sampling techniques can also be used to get appropriate and better results.

5.5 Conclusion

Results of the study reveal that all the job stressors show negative and significant effect with job performance. Mean role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development and role responsibility being job stressors affect the job performance of police personnel of KPK inversely. Evidences of the study show that the higher level or more intensity in the job stressors impact badly the performance level of police's individuals. The lower intensity in the stress level arise due to job stressors is the reason to boost up their (police employees) performance. Besides this, all the job stressors are found significantly associated with the employees performance. Means the findings of the study support H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄ and H₅.

Rest of the hypotheses present the moderation effect of workplace spirituality between job stressors (role overload, role conflict, role ambiguity, career development, role responsibility) and job performance. There is observed moderation effect of workplace spirituality between all of the study job stressors and job performance. Hypothesis H₆ illustrates that workplace spirituality plays as a moderating role between job stressors and job performance. Hence, results indicate that H₆ is proved.

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